

D6.9 Communication and dissemination plan - First Report

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-SC5-2019-2 GA No. 869565
Project title	Vineyard Innovative Tool based on the InteGration of Earth Observation Services and in-field Sensors
Duration of the project	September 2020 - February 2024 (42 months)
WP/Task:	WP6
Document due Date:	31/03/2021
Actual date of delivery	31/03/2021
Leader of this deliverable	EUT / BSC
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Submitted

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	02/03/2021	Marina Presas (EUT)	Draft version
0.2	15/03/2021	Marta Terrado, Andria Nicodemou (BSC)	Draft completion
0.3	20/03/2021	Marina Presas (EUT)	Consolidation of first version for partners' review
1.0	29/03/2021	Andria Nicodemou (BSC), Josep Pijuan (EUT), Ernesto Bastidas (ELEAF)	Peer review
2.0	30/03/2021	Marina Presas (EUT), Andria Nicodemou (BSC)	Production of final version
3.0	31/03/2021	Rosa Araujo (EUT)	Project coordinator review

Executive summary

The present public document details the VitiGEOSS project dissemination and communication plan, aiming at reaching as many relevant actors as possible to inform them on the activities and results derived from the project. BSC and EUT are responsible for designing and implementing VitiGEOSS communication and dissemination strategy, but all consortium partners will be involved in it.

The channels and platforms considered in the communication and dissemination plan are: social media channels, official website, materials to be distributed in key events, media relations to specialized media outlets, scientific publications, the organization of workshops and training activities, and attendance to strategic conferences, fairs and congresses where the project can be presented and the organisation of stakeholder engagement events, among others.

This deliverable details the target groups, key messages addressed to each main group of stakeholders, communication and dissemination activities planned, requirements and the process of reporting and monitoring communication activities.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information sheet	2
Executive summary.....	2
Table of contents	3
List of figures	4
List of tables	4
List of abbreviations	5
Introduction	5
1. Communication and dissemination plan	6
1.1 Target audience	6
1.2 Channels.....	8
1.3 Key messages	8
2. Communication and dissemination management.....	10
2.1 Distribution of responsibilities	10
2.2 Acknowledgements	11
2.3 Monitoring and reporting.....	11
2.3.1 Activities reporting.....	11
2.3.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	12
2.3.3 KPI reporting	13
2.4 Risks and mitigation measures	16
3. Communication and dissemination tools and activities	17
3.1 Project Visual Identity materials.....	17
3.2 Website.....	17
3.3 Promotional materials.....	17
3.3.1 Digital & print promotional materials.....	18
3.3.2 Executive summary.....	18
3.3.3 Audio-visual materials.....	18
3.4 Social Media Strategy.....	19
3.4.1 Twitter	19
3.4.2 YouTube.....	22
3.4.3 Partners' channels.....	22
3.5 Media relations	23
3.5.1 Press release proposed calendar.....	25
3.6 Academic Dissemination	25
3.6.1 Participation to conferences and congresses	25
3.6.2 Scientific publications.....	26
3.7 Dissemination to the industry	27
3.7.1 Participation in industry events.....	27

3.7.2 Technical webinars	28
3.7.3 Local stakeholder sessions.....	29
3.7.4 Participatory workshops	29
3.8 Dissemination to the society.....	30
3.9 Clustering activities and joint dissemination actions	30
3.9.1 Sister projects.....	30
3.9.2 EU initiatives and key platforms.....	33
4. Activities calendar	34

List of figures

Figure 1: Initial stakeholders' map.....	7
Figure 2: VitiGEOSS Dissemination and Communication Channels	8
Figure 3: View of the project's home page.....	17
Figure 4: View of VitiGEOSS Twitter account	19
Figure 5: View of Twitter Analytics	22

List of tables

Table 1: Table to record the communication and dissemination activities performed by partners.....	11
Table 2: Communication and Dissemination KPIs.....	12
Table 3: List of deliverables on communication and dissemination activities.....	13
Table 4: Table for tracking web and social media analytics.....	14
Table 5: Table to report scientific publications	15
Table 6: Media clipping table	15
Table 7: Risks and mitigation measures	16
Table 8: Partners' social media accounts.....	23
Table 9: Initial list of specialised outlets.....	24
Table 10: Press release plan	25
Table 11: Identified list of academic conferences and congresses	25
Table 12: List of open access journals.....	27
Table 13: Identified events targeting the industry community.....	27
Table 14: Webinars tentative dates and topics.....	28
Table 15: Preliminary dates of local stakeholder sessions	29
Table 16: Planned workshops	30
Table 17: VitiGEOSS sister projects	31

List of abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EO	Earth Observation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PR	Public relations
WP	Work Package

Introduction

VitiGEOSS is a 3-year and a half project aiming to promote the use of European open Earth observation (EO) services, developing an **innovative vineyard management tool based on the integration of EO and in-field sensors** to increase the resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to the viticulture sector.

The project also has the objective to respond to future challenges of the worldwide food and wine industry, which require **intensification of the production in a sustainable way, mitigating the effects of climate change, reducing negative environmental externalities and promoting local economic growth.**

The VitiGEOSS Communication and Dissemination Plan aims to outline the communication and dissemination activities planned throughout the project. These activities aim to **raise awareness** on the project and its **results** among the target audiences and as many relevant actors as possible, **support exploitation** and ensure market uptake of the developed platform, and **share the know-how generated** from the project with the scientific and industrial community.

This document includes the creation and maintenance of the project's website, social media channels and posts, the creation of promotional materials, press releases, scientific publications, the organization of workshops, training activities and stakeholder engagement events, and the attendance to strategic conferences, fairs, congresses and other events. It also includes the dissemination objectives, key messages for the different target audiences and timing of activities. Key performance indicators (KPIs) for each communication and dissemination activity will be defined and reported, ensuring the traceability of the activities that are not listed under particular deliverables or milestones.

1. Communication and dissemination plan

The main goals of the VitiGEOSS project communication and dissemination strategy are:

- **Increase the visibility** of VitiGEOSS and its outcomes in Europe and beyond
- Develop communication and dissemination activities to **facilitate knowledge transfer** to stakeholders
- Promote the use of **Earth Observation services and Climate services** in the agriculture sector
- **Build capacity** among current and potential developers and users of commercial products within the wine sector and beyond
- **Showcase new capabilities** combining smart services and make them **available for uptake** by the European wine industry and global markets

The main language of the communication and dissemination activities organised by VitiGEOSS will be English. However, specific materials will be translated into Spanish, Italian and Portuguese for a broader reach, with support from EUT (Spanish), LINKS and UNINA (Italian), and SYM (Portuguese).

1.1 Target audience

Five stakeholder groups have been identified as the target audience of the communication and dissemination activities, including: academia, industry, end-users/customers, policy makers, and society at large. Detailed information on identified stakeholder groups is presented in Figure 1.

A list of key contacts and target stakeholders has been prepared and is stored in the VitiGEOSS internal collaborative platform (ensuring that no personal information is included or distributed). This list will be regularly updated with new contacts, including individuals who sign-up to the project mailing list through a form circulated on the project communication channels.

Scientific and academic community

- Universities, institutes and research centers on researching Earth Observation (remote sensing, geoanalysis), climate forecasting, phenology, vine fertilisation and disease monitoring, sensing, applied artificial intelligence, etc.
- Research and technology organizations
- Attendees to trade exhibitions covering the project's fields (EU Conference on precision agriculture, EuroGEOSS workshop, ONEOVITI Interlational, International Organisation of Vine and Wine, etc.)
- Sister projects (VISCA, e-shape, ENVISION, SAFERS, NextLand, SUSTUNTECH, FIRE, etc.)

Industry, end users / customers

- Farmers, wine producers, R&D technicians working in the wine sector, EU wine industry, downstream operators (wine producers and distributors), upstream operators (fertilised producers)
- Viticulture sector and ICT companies and companies in the agriculture value chain (machinery, applications, etc.).
- Wine cooperatives, agricultural organisations, clusters (e.g. INNOVI, Plataforma tecnológica del vino, Confederação dos Agricultores de Portugal (CAP), CONFAGRICOLTURA, CCBUL, Irish farmer's association, FEV - the Spanish Wine Federation, etc.)
- Climate services and Earth Observations industrial community (companies providing services) (e.g. EARSC - European Association of Remote Sensing Companies)
- Industrial trade fairs and exhibitions (VINITALY, VINEXPO, ALIMENTARIA, Fair of Agricultural Machinery, wine fairs, etc.)

Policy makers

- Governmental bodies in charge of agricultural resources management (e.g. Departments / Ministries of Agriculture) and environment, Governmental Wine Institutions / Institutes (INCAVI, VITINNOV), European bodies managing earth observations (Copernicus, European Space Agency, etc.)
- Networks, associations, platforms (COPA-COGECA, Comité Européen des entreprises vins, EuroGEO, COPTA, etc.)
- Environmental organisations
- Other initiatives (EU wine market observatory)
- Standardisation bodies and technical committees.

Society at large

- Rural communities
- Mass media
- Wine consumers, consumers associations (WWCA - World Wine Consumer Association, International Wine Clubs Association, OCU - Spanish Consumers Association, etc.).
- Wine sector top influencers (GLOBAL: Madeline Puckette, Maximilian Riedel, Kelly Mitchell, Carolyn Evens Hammond, Jamie Goode, Liz Palmer, Meg Maker - Terrior Review, Joey Casco - TheWineStalker, Andrea Zigrassi, Gaetano Saccoccio - Natura Delle Cose FRANCE: Emmanuel Delmas, Louise Binns, Nicolas de Rouyn, Fabiel Lainé, Marina Giuberti, Julien Miquel, Tanisha Townsend, UK: Tim Atkin, Jancis Robinson, Fiona Beckett SPAIN: José Pañín, Josep Roca, Amaya Cervera - Spanish Wine Lover, Luis Gutiérrez Santo Domingo ITALY: Andrea Zigrassi, Francesco Saverio Russo)
- EU citizens

Figure 1: Initial stakeholders' map

1.2 Channels

The dissemination and communication activities of the VitiGEOSS project use a wide range of channels and actions, ranging from publication of project results and news on the project website and social media channels, preparation of promotional materials, scientific publications, organisation of workshops and specific stakeholder engagement events, to the representation of the project in key events (see Figure 2).

Besides the aforementioned project channels, all partners will make use of their own channels (websites, presence on social media and corporate newsletters / publications) to disseminate news about VitiGEOSS and reach a broader audience.

Figure 2: VitiGEOSS Dissemination and Communication Channels

1.3 Key messages

A number of key messages have been defined, which will be evolved throughout the project and tailored according to the target audience, including both specialists and non-specialists, in order to enhance the reach of the project research, actions and results.

General VitiGEOSS messages include:

1. *The VitiGEOSS project uses European Open Earth Observation Services (EOS) and Climate Services for the improvement of agriculture business operations at an economic, environmental and local level.*
2. *VitiGEOSS project develops innovative vineyard management solutions by integrating and improving existing tools that couple satellite imagery with in-field sensors.*
3. *VitiGEOSS will be the first application offering integrated services for weather and climate predictions, crop management, disease management, business operations and sustainability assessment.*
4. *VitiGEOSS project will respond to current and future viticulture challenges by providing forecasts, data and recommendations to wine producers to optimise vineyard management.*
5. *VitiGEOSS is a EU H2020 project that will boost vineyard sustainability while adapting to climate change.*

Academia

- The VitiGEOSS project will advance the state-of-the-art techniques for weather and climate forecasts, monitoring of crop phenological stages as well as irrigation and

fertilization needs, prediction of phenology stages and yield, and disease early prediction, risk assessment and recommendations on treatments.

- The VitiGEOSS platform will be fed with free-of-charge satellite imagery, other Earth Observation and climate prediction products from the European Copernicus Programme and NASA, coupled with in-field and near in-field data to extract useful indicators for a better management of vineyards and optimisation of agricultural practices.
- Machine Learning and new mathematical models will be used to detect and predict the vineyards phenology states based on weather observations, weather forecasts, in-field cameras and satellite imagery to support a better planning of operations.
- Key crop indicators will be used for the zonal delineation of vineyards to help define precision agriculture management strategies.
- Artificial Intelligence techniques will be used for the analysis and integration of multiple data sources to develop novel disease management and resource optimisation services.
- The scientific results of VitiGEOSS will be openly available to support further research activities.

Industry, consumers and end users

- The project will offer to the viticulture sector a commercial and web platform, integrating information from intelligent services to support farmers and producers to optimise vineyard management processes by making the most of open European data and resources.
- The project will validate the potential benefits of data fusion techniques for monitoring vineyards which could derive in a downscaling of the decision-making area granularity offered by Copernicus based solutions. This would produce better management strategies and costs optimization, by also supporting sustainable practices.
- VitiGEOSS will provide sub-seasonal and seasonal climate predictions, recommendations for crop and disease management, and tools for the management of business operations and sustainability of the vineyard.
- The VitiGEOSS platform will help farmers tackle most critical vineyard diseases scheduling the preventive treatments according to diseases evolution, using less chemicals and adapting their production methods to minimise damages to the environment.
- The VitiGEOSS information services will help schedule optimal harvesting days and thus contribute to optimize the harvesting process and consequent winemaking, minimising the waste of resources and increasing the competitiveness of vineyards.
- The VitiGEOSS services will be validated in three vineyards located in Italy, Spain and Portugal before their release.

Policy makers

- VitiGEOSS will help the agriculture sector adapt to climate change and thus minimise the use of recovery plans for weather-affected crops.
- The proposed solution promotes the potential of the Copernicus programme and European satellite data for agriculture.
- The VitiGEOSS information services will advance the development of services based on the use of Earth Observation Services.
- The VitiGEOSS platform will provide valuable information to public administrations to support the design of environmental and agriculture policies as well as subsidies/funds in the event of emergencies, such as extreme weather events with critical effects for the harvest.

Society at large

- The implementation of the VitiGEOSS solution will contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions through the optimisation of operations that involve the use of fossil fuels.
- The solution will help reduce the amount of chemicals used in the fields, resulting in more sustainable practices for the environment and healthier wines for the EU consumers.
- The innovative solutions promoted by the project help mitigate the effects of climate change, reducing negative environmental externalities and promoting local economic growth.

2. Communication and dissemination management

2.1 Distribution of responsibilities

The VitiGEOSS dissemination and communication strategy foresees the active involvement and commitment of all project partners for presenting the project and its outcomes.

WP6 includes the following tasks with several subtasks:

- **Task 6.1 - Communication and dissemination management** (EUT, BSC, all partners)
 - **Subtask 6.1.1. Visual Identity and Website** (EUT)
 - **Subtask 6.1.2. Communication and dissemination plan** (EUT, BSC)
 - **Subtask 6.1.3. Communication and PR materials** (EUT, BSC)
- **Task 6.2 - Capacity building among industrial partners and other stakeholders** (BSC, EUT, ELEAF, UNINA, LINKS)
 - **Subtask 6.2.1. Technical webinars** (BSC, EUT)
 - **Subtask 6.2.2. Participatory workshops** (ELEAF, BSC, UNINA, LINKS, EUT)
 - **Subtask 6.2.3. Demo video** (EUT, BSC, LINKS, ELEAF, UNINA)
- **Task 6.3 - Knowledge transfer and added value provision to target groups** (BSC, ELEAF, MBD, MTSA, SYM, EUT, LINKS, UNINA)
 - **Subtask 6.3.1. Sharing lessons learned with Climate Services and Earth Observations communities** (BSC, ELEAF)
 - **Subtask 6.3.2. Local stakeholder sessions at General Assemblies** (EUT, MBD, MTSA, SYM, UNINA)
 - **Subtask 6.3.3. Executive summary** (BSC, EUT, PWC, ELEAF, all partners)

BSC is the Communication and Dissemination lead beneficiary, responsible for **coordinating WP6 activities**, ensuring the proper information exchange within the consortium and supporting the full dissemination of the project and its results. In addition, BSC will lead the organisation of three technical webinars (Subtask 6.2.1), the work on sharing the lessons learned in the project with the Climate Services community (Subtask 6.3.1), and the production of an executive summary at the end of the project highlighting the main results (Subtask 6.3.3).

EUT, through its Research Communication Office (RCO), will **support BSC in coordinating the WP** and will be the **partner directly responsible** for the development of the project's visual identity and website (Subtask 6.1.1). EUT will also be responsible for the **production of the Communication and Dissemination Plan** (Subtask 6.1.2), the **production of communication and PR materials** and a demo video (Subtasks 6.1.3 and 6.2.3), and the coordination overview of the local stakeholder sessions at the General Assemblies. The RTO will also participate on the organisation of technical webinars.

End-users **MBD**, **MTSA** and **SYM** will organise a local stakeholder session at their facilities to engage local farmers and rural communities (Subtask 6.3.2).

In addition, **ELEAF** will lead the organisation of the participatory workshops (Subtask 6.2.2) and will be responsible for sharing the lessons learned in the project with the Earth Observations community. **BSC** and **UNINA** will play an active role by developing the contents for and participating in the trainings and seminars organised during the workshops.

2.2 Acknowledgements

All communication and dissemination materials produced in the project (posters, presentations, promotional material, publications, etc.) and distributed in physical or electronic format (e.g. social media) will display the EU emblem and funding text provided below, in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869565.

In addition, results disseminated are recommended to include the following disclaimer:

[This result NAME] reflects only the author's view and the Agency / Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Scientific papers based on the research conducted in the project will be published in open-access repositories, mentioning in the acknowledgements the VitiGEOSS project name, as well as that funding was received by the European Union (EU)/Horizon 2020 (including grant number).

2.3 Monitoring and reporting

2.3.1 Activities reporting

An Excel file has been prepared by the BSC to register all communication and dissemination activities done by partners during the project execution.

This file is located in the Sharepoint online repository that is available to all partners and contains a description of the activity, the target audience, date and location, the partners involved, the number of people reached, feedback received and information about which WP/Task was associated with the activity.

Table 1: Table to record the communication and dissemination activities performed by partners

Type of action	Primary audience reached with the action	Secondary audience reached	Title of the action	Location	Date	Number of people reached	of	Link	VitiGEOSS attendees/organisers (if applicable)

2.3.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPIs have been assigned to a number of communication and dissemination activities planned in the project in order to assess their performance and impact by the end of the project (M42). These are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M42
Website	Number of website visits	Website Analytics	>3,500
	Number of pages viewed		>10,000
	Number of users		>1,500
	Average session time		>1 min
Social Media	Twitter: Number of followers	Twitter Analytics	>200
	Twitter: Number of tweets		>300
	Twitter: Twitter impressions		>50,000
	Twitter: Likes on tweets		>100
	Twitter: Retweets		>30
	Twitter: Mentions		>20
	YouTube: Number of videos uploaded	YouTube Analytics	>5
	YouTube: Number of video views		>300
Press Releases	Number of press releases	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>4
	Articles published in EU outlets		>25
Events	Number of events participated (congresses, conferences, etc.)	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>20
	Number of local stakeholder sessions organised		3
	Number of technical webinars organised		3
	Number of participatory workshops organised		2
Publications	Number of scientific publications	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	5
	Number of articles in specialised magazines / outlets		3
Visual Materials	Number of posters produced	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	4
	Number of info-sheets produced		6
	Audio-visual materials		>2
	Project public reports		5
	Number of executive summaries		1
	Number of roll-ups		1
	Number of brochures		1

2.3.3 KPI reporting

The progress of KPIs until the end of the project will be reported in project deliverables (see Table 32).

Table 3: List of deliverables on communication and dissemination activities

Deliverable No	Deliverable name	Lead	Type	Diss. level	Date
D6.1	Visual identity and project website available	EURECAT	R	PU	M3
D6.2	Middle summary report on user engagement activities	BSC	R	CO	M27
D6.3	Initial summary report on user engagement activities	BSC	R	CO	M12
D6.4	Summary report on dissemination and communication activities and materials	BSC	R	CO	M42
D6.5	Final summary report on user engagement activities	BSC	R	CO	M42
D6.6	Demo video	EURECAT	DEC	PU	M24
D6.7	Lessons learned for the Climate Services and Earth Observations communities	BSC	R	PU	M36
D6.8	Executive summary	BSC	R	PU	M42
D6.9	Communication and dissemination plan - first report	EURECAT	R	PU	M7
D6.10	Communication and dissemination plan - final report	EURECAT	R	PU	M18
D6.11	Demo video - second version	EURECAT	DEC	PU	M40
D6.12	Summary report on dissemination and communication activities and materials - first version	BSC	R	CO	M36

In addition, to facilitate the reporting, an Excel file has been prepared to record the monthly progress of KPIs. The file is stored in the shared WP6 folder (accessible by all partners) and includes the following sections:

- **Web and Social Media:** to report the progress on project and partner channels

Table 4: Table for tracking web and social media analytics

KPIs VitiGEOSS Digital Channels	M1 Sep-20	M2 Oct-20	M3 Nov20	M4 Dec-20	M5 Jan-20
VitiGEOSS Twitter Account					
#Followers					
#New Followers					
#Total Tweets					
#New Tweets					
# Impressions					
# Mentions					
# Likes on Tweets					
# Retweets					
Twitter accounts Partners					
EUT					
# Tweets					
# Likes					
#Retweets					
LINKS					
BSC					
ELEAF					
PWC					
SYM					
MTSA					
UNINA					
TOTAL (aggregate)					
LinkedIn - Partners accounts					
EUT					
LINKS					
BSC					
ELEAF					
MTSA					
PWC					
UNINA					
TOTAL (aggregate)					
#Posts					
#Likes					
#Comments					
#Shares					
Facebook - partners accounts					
EUT					
LINKS					
BSC					
MTSA					
MBD					
PWC					
UNINA					
TOTAL (aggregate)					
Web Analytics					
# Web visits					
Avg. session time					
#Pages Viewed					

# Actions / session					
#Users					
# Downloads					

- **Scientific papers:** for tracking on-going and published papers

Table 5: Table to report scientific publications

Type of scientific publication	Title of the scientific publication	DOI	ISSN	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent
[Article in journal]		-			
[Conference proceeding /workshop]					
[Books/ Monographies]					
[Chapter in Books]					

Number, date	Publisher	Place of publication	Year	Relevant pages	Peer-review	Is/Will open access
					YES / NO	YES / NO

- **Media Clipping:** for recording articles in general and specialised media outlets

Table 6: Media clipping table

ONLINE						
Date	Media	Title	Audience	Economic Value	Link	
PRINT						
Date	Media	Title	Readers	Circulation	Economic Value	Link
TOTAL	# of articles					
2021						
2022						
2023						
2024						

2.4 Risks and mitigation measures

The risks faced in the completion of activities planned in WP6 and potential mitigation measures have been defined and are presented in Table 3. This table will be reviewed periodically to spot any new risks and determine if there is a need to put in place mitigation actions.

Table 7: Risks and mitigation measures

Risks	Risk level	Mitigation measures
Not enough users reached to provide a sustainable operation of the VITIGE OSS portal and services	Medium	Dedicated communication and dissemination strategies will be developed to ensure that a sufficient user-base can be reached. Involvement of relevant initiatives in the project Advisory Board that can help reach additional users.
Low stakeholder engagement in webinars, workshops and local sessions	Medium	Intensive communication campaigns promoting the activities through relevant channels will be run minimum 2 months in advance. Take advantage of project partners involved in relevant EU projects and initiatives to serve as ambassadors of VitiGEOSS and multiply project dissemination and stakeholder engagement.
Not enough dissemination opportunities due to COVID-19 effects	High	Thorough identification of activities and organisation of own events. Stronger emphasis on the organisation of online project activities (such as webinars) and possibility to accommodate initially planned physical activities remotely. Higher reliance on online channels (e.g. social media).
Not enough engagement on VitiGEOSS communication channels	Medium	Creation of more content for the project website and social media that engages stakeholders, increase the frequency of publication on project channels
Low project visibility	Low	Develop an appealing website and communication materials. Organise joint activities with other initiatives and projects (e.g. e-Shape, NextGEOSS)

3. Communication and dissemination tools and activities

3.1 Project Visual Identity materials

EUT has been in charge of defining the project’s image to be implemented across all the communication and dissemination channels, including the design of the logo, colour palette, and deliverable and presentation templates. EUT will ensure the correct use of the visual identity in all project-related materials. For more information regarding the VitiGEOSS visual identity, please refer to **D6.1 - Visual Identity and Project Website**.

3.2 Website

The project website (www.vitigeoss.eu) was launched in November 2020, as defined in **D6.1 Visual Identity and Project Website**. It has served since its creation as the main information platform for users interested in knowing more about VitiGEOSS. The website displays the project’s basic information, objectives, scenarios and expected outputs. Furthermore, the website is the central repository for all public material, including public results and deliverables, and gives access to the project’s Twitter channel.

The website will be regularly updated by EUT with dissemination activities, media appearances and new deliverables, among other materials.

Figure 3: View of the project’s home page

3.3 Promotional materials

EUT and BSC will be in charge of creating all visual material to support the project’s dissemination activities and events, such as conferences, congresses, workshops or project events (local stakeholder sessions, webinars, etc.).

Three types of materials will be produced: promotional material to print or use digitally, a final executive summary and audio-visual materials.

All materials will be stored digitally in the project's internal repository and on the project website for broader dissemination. Promotional materials will be regularly updated according to the project developments. Materials oriented to end-users will be translated into Spanish, Italian and Portuguese, responding to the VitiGEOSS project needs.

3.3.1 Digital & print promotional materials

EUT has designed and produced different types of promotional materials by month 5 of the project, including a **factsheet**, a **rollup**, a **trifold**, a **poster layout** and a **general presentation** to support the partners' dissemination activities.

All materials follow the project's visual identity guidelines (mentioned in section 3.1) and are available to all consortium members in a digital format. The materials are also available publicly on the project's website in the page "**Newsletters & Promotional Materials**".

This set of materials will be updated at different stages of the project to include up-to-date information of the advances and results (M20, M32, M40).

Other materials are planned to be produced during the project, including a **poster summarising the VitiGEOSS concept and platform** (planned for M20), which will be translated into the end-user's native languages - Spanish, Portuguese and Italian - and **6 infosheets on the VitiGEOSS information services** to facilitate the transfer of the knowledge generated in the project into a wider audience (prepared in M32, and updated in M40).

3.3.2 Executive summary

Based on the project publications and public deliverables, an executive summary will be produced by M42 (as part of Subtask 6.3.3) to compile VitiGEOSS relevant results, impact and conclusions. The document aims to make the project conclusions easier to understand by policy makers and non-specialised audiences. Graphic materials gathered during the discussions in consortium meetings and stakeholder-oriented events (especially if there are opportunities for physical gatherings) will be used for the elaboration of the document.

The executive summary will be produced by the BSC with support from all partners, and will be disseminated broadly on the VitiGEOSS website and other project channels (such as Twitter), as well as shared directly with any relevant contacts.

3.3.3 Audio-visual materials

Engaging audio-visual materials (e.g. videos) will be produced to present the key aspects of the project, including the project's deployment of information services and platform and its validation into demonstration sites.

Audio-visual material produced within the project framework will be published on the VitiGEOSS website and promoted on all project social media channels (Twitter & YouTube). A number of videos are planned, including the following:

- **Videos of short interviews** (M12 - M18)- Short interviews with project partners about topics related to the project (Earth observations in agriculture, agritech, satellite and in-field observations, phenological and climate forecasting models, geoanalysis etc.). EUT, together with BSC, will decide on the topics of interest for the audience of the project and will prepare the interview questions (sent in advance to partners) to produce short video interviews. The videos will be recorded during consortium meetings

or recorded remotely (e.g. using Microsoft Teams), and then edited and published by EUT.

- **Intelligent services / platform demo videos (M24 - M40)** - A series of videos that guide users through the different smart services developed in WP2 and the portal deployed by WP3 will be produced. These videos will also provide the necessary context to understand the project challenges, motivations and outcomes.
- **Final video (M41 - M42)** - A video compiling the results of the project, its applications and its benefits for the EU wine sector will be produced by EUT. It will include images on the work done in each of the pilot sites and short interviews with users, pilot site representatives and VitiGEOSS partners.

The production of other audio-visual materials will be evaluated among the consortium if any other opportunities arise. Partners will be able to propose other video topics and produce complementary videos on their contribution to VitiGEOSS project.

All videos will be produced in English, with subtitles available in Spanish, Italian and Portuguese to facilitate comprehension in the three pilot countries.

3.4 Social Media Strategy

EUT is responsible for managing the VitiGEOSS social media accounts and its content. A Twitter channel for VitiGEOSS has already been created (@Vitigeoss_EU) and is used to promote project materials and news. A YouTube channel will be created as soon as the first project video is available.

Other social media accounts, such as LinkedIn and Facebook, are not currently planned. However, the need and benefits of creating these accounts will be reviewed and revisited later on in the project and addressed in the updates of the Communication and Dissemination Plan.

All partners will contribute spreading the word on their corporate and personal Social Media channels, including accounts in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn or Instagram.

The project coordinator will be in charge of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels.

3.4.1 Twitter

Figure 4: View of VitiGEOSS Twitter account

The VitiGEOSS Twitter account will be managed by EUT, with the support of project partners for its correct management. The main objective of this account is to raise awareness on the potential application of Earth Observation Services to enhance the sustainability of the wine industry, as well as to promote the project's intelligent services and platform to key stakeholders and the wine sector value chain. Twitter will be also used to connect with EU institutions and related projects and initiatives.

Relevant stakeholders and partners with a professional Twitter account will be followed by the VitiGEOSS account in order to boost the visibility of the account.

3.4.1.1 Account Management

EUT will create a regular plan of content to be disseminated through the VitiGEOSS Twitter account. All consortium partners can propose content (text, images, videos...) to be distributed in this channel and spread the word through their own social media channels by sharing and engaging with the content.

A Hootsuite account, a tool facilitating the publication of content and activity monitoring, has been created for scheduling tweets and shortening URLs. Comments and answers will be managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

3.4.1.2 Content Strategy

When creating and publishing content about the project, EUT and the rest of the partners will consider the following recommendations in order to maximise the impact of the messages.

The strategy mixes marketing content, branding and influence actions to maximise the project's impact, and encourages market uptake to secure a critical mass of early adopters of the smart services and platform among the viticulture sector.

Content strategy:

- **Disseminating project activities:** sharing information on stakeholder engagement events, workshops, technical webinars and other dissemination activities organised by the project, including text and photos if possible.
- **Content curation:** sharing news on Earth Observation Services, Copernicus, phenology and climate forecasting models, sustainable agriculture case studies, technologies for the agricultural and viticulture sectors, disease management, business operation management, irrigation and yield prediction, etc.
- **Disseminating audio-visual and promotional materials produced** (to make the project more accessible/understandable).
- **Sharing news and articles published on the website** to increase traffic.
- To increase the reach of the tweets, the frequent use of the following hashtags is proposed:
 - **Project:** #VitiGEOSS #VitiGEOSSproject #ResearchImpactEu #Horizon2020 #H2020 #research
 - **Wine sector:** #wine #wines #viticulture #viticultors #grapes #vineyards #agriculture #winemakers #vinegrowers #agritech #agrifood #vine #plantscience #harvest #phenology #sustainability #grapegrowers #plantdisease
 - **Information services:** #EOS #EuroGEO #earthobservation #GEOSS #ArtificialIntelligence #AI #remotesensing #climateservices #climatechange #climate #Copernicus #EO #space #aerospace #geospatial #satelliteimagery #innovation
- **Project partners** (@Eurecat_news, @LinksFoundation @SymingtonFamily @eleaf @BSC_CNS @FamiliaTorres @Torreswines) **will be mentioned** when publishing news about them to promote likes and retweets from partners.
- **Accounts and content from projects funded under the same topic** (@VISCA_2020, @e_shape_eu, @NextGEOSS, @SAFERS, @EnvisionH2020, @NextLand_EO, @medgold_H2020 @agROBOfood @RIS3_Copta @SmartAgriHubs @Robs4crops

@DihAgrifood @EUCP_H2020 @InnosetaNetwork, Coppereplace etc.) will also be mentioned and retweeted.

Branding strategy:

- Twitter posts will be prepared covering fairs, trade shows, congresses and other events where VitiGEOSS participates, using the official hashtag of the event (e.g. European Conference of Precision Agriculture #ECPA2019, EnoForum Conference #enoforumwebconference2021, Vinitaly #Vinitaly2021, VINEXPO #VINEXPO, etc.).
- The official VitiGEOSS Twitter account will be referenced in the partner's corporate accounts for a broader reach of the project.

Influencer strategy:

- Accounts such as @EU_H2020 @EuScienceInnov @CORDIS_EU @EU_commission @EUClimateAction @Copernicus @EO_OPEN_SCIENCE @GEOSEC2025 @earsc @EUAgri @opengeospatial @COPAGOGECA @EuroGeosciences @eumetsat @EUClimateAction @grapidp will be regularly mentioned in tweets in order to get a bigger impact when project news or information about results is published.
- Influencers in the field of Earth Observation Services, Satellite Imaging, wine and vineyard innovation technologies, among other topics will be identified and mentioned in relevant posts.
- Stakeholder's accounts will be identified to promote follow-back and to increase the number of VitiGEOSS followers.
- Media will be mentioned if they are publishing information about the project.

3.4.1.3 Analytics

A profile in Twitter Analytics has been activated in order to measure the Twitter KPIs (see Section 2.3.2 for more information) and other data about the account activity. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Figure 5: View of Twitter Analytics

3.4.2 YouTube

The European Commission recommends the use of audio-visual resources to bring the results of the research projects closer to the general public.

Following this recommendation, a YouTube Channel will be created to allocate all videos produced during the project as soon as the first video is ready. Videos will be shared on the website and on project's social media accounts for a broader impact.

3.4.3 Partners' channels

Each partner will transmit VitiGE OSS news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents published on www.vitigeoss-project.eu or in the project Twitter account.

VitiGE OSS' partners impact in social media channels will reach more than **53K users on Twitter**, more than **112K on LinkedIn**, more than **1M Facebook followers** and **59K** in Instagram.

Some of the corporate accounts used by partners are:

Table 8: Partners' social media accounts

PARTNER	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook	Instagram
EUT	https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/	@Eurecat_News	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/	NA
LINKS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/linksfoundation/	@LinksFoundation	https://www.facebook.com/linksfoundation	NA
SYM	NA	@SymingtonFamily	NA	@symingtonfamilyestates
ELEAF	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eleaf/	@eleaf	NA	NA
BSC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/barcelona-supercomputing-center/	@BSC_CNS	https://www.facebook.com/BSCCNS	@BSC_CNS
PwC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/pwc-portugal	NA	https://www.facebook.com/pwcpportugal	@pwc_portugal
UNINA	NA	NA	NA	NA
MBD	NA	NA	https://www.facebook.com/MastroberardinoVineyards	@mastroberardinowinery
MTSA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/familiatorres	@FamiliaTorres @Torreswines	https://www.facebook.com/familiatorresofficial	@FamiliaTorres1870 @Familiatorreswines

3.5 Media relations

Press releases will be written and sent to relevant media at regular intervals throughout the project, focusing on the release of research results, milestones, meetings, attendance to or organisation of events etc., and connected with newsworthy initiatives when possible (e.g. EU Green Week, Rural Conventions, etc.).

All press releases will be distributed among partners in English for providing feedback (where appropriate), giving them the opportunity to adapt the documents in their corporate language and to circulate it among their regional media contacts.

Apart from consortium press releases, country-focused press releases or press releases oriented to a specific stakeholder group may be elaborated by partners, after informing the Project Coordinator and Communication Leader (EUT). Also, VitiGEOSS partners will consider interview-offerings and a press conference at the end of the project to showcase the main project results to media.

In the framework of the project, a **database with the contact details of partners' communication officers has been created**, to facilitate the review of the media materials, coordinate the sending of the press releases and increase the project impact across Europe.

A database with specialised media covering Earth Observation Services and innovations / technologies for the wine sector will be created, primarily with outlets located in the partners' countries.

An initial list of **European / Global specialised media outlets** identified as relevant to promote VitiGEOSS outputs include:

Table 9: Initial list of specialised outlets

LIST OF SPECIALISED OUTLETS	Language
Mon-Viti - https://www.mon-viti.com	French
Future Farming - https://www.futurefarming.com	English
Geospatial world - https://www.geospatialworld.net	English
E&T Engineering and Technology - https://eandt.theiet.org/tags/earth-observation	English
InfoWine - https://www.infowine.com/en/news/news_cat_23.htm#	English
Vitisphere - https://www.vitisphere.com/world-wine-0-0-0-news.htm	English
WineSpectator - https://www.winespectator.com/news	English
HortNews - https://hortnews.com/articles/horticulture-news/viticulture-news/	English
DownToEarth - https://www.downtoearth.org.in	English
Tech.eu - https://tech.eu/about-us/	English
Farmers' weekly - https://www.fwi.co.uk	English
Farmers Guardian - https://www.fginsight.com	English
InfoAgro.com - https://www.infoagro.com/noticias/?ids=8	Spanish
La Semana Vitivinícola - http://www.sevi.net/es/3578/94/	Spanish
Vinetur - https://www.vinetur.com	Spanish
FuturENVIRO - https://futurenviro.es	Spanish
Agroinformación - https://agroinformacion.com	Spanish
Agroportal - https://www.agroportal.pt/autor/agroinformacion/	Spanish
El Correo del Vino - https://elcorreodelvino.com	Spanish
Enovicultura - https://enovicultura.quatrebcn.es	Spanish

3.5.1 Press release proposed calendar

An initial calendar of press releases to be written is as follows:

Table 10: Press release plan

VitiGEOSS press release plan		Partners responsible
M10	1 st press release of the project (work done, expected outputs)	EUT, BSC
M20	Release of intelligent services	EUT, BSC, LINKS, ELEAF
M30	Start of services validation in pilot sites (SYM, MTSA, MBD). Adaptation into three country-focused press releases.	EUT, SYM, MTSA, MBD
M40	Platform release	EUT, ELEAF
M42	Final project results.	EUT, BSC, SYM, MTSA, MBD

3.6 Academic Dissemination

3.6.1 Participation to conferences and congresses

Participation in national and international conferences, congresses and workshops targeting the academic and scientific community is essential to transfer the knowledge acquired during the project. A wide range of conferences and academic fora are suitable for the exhibition and publication of the VitiGEOSS' results, covering, but not limited, the topics of precision agriculture, earth observation services, climate & weather forecasting, smart agriculture, etc.

Dissemination will mainly focus on the partners' countries (Italy, Spain, and Portugal). Partners will also consider attending events taking place in other European countries targeting communities strongly related to the project objectives, certainly including the agriculture and wine community, but also the EO community as well as other stakeholders for which the methodological approach and results of the project could be of interest (climate services community, Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) communities, etc.).

A non-exhaustive list of events already identified as relevant to disseminate VitiGEOSS activities and outcomes are presented in table 11. The list will be periodically updated by partners.

Table 11: Identified list of academic conferences and congresses

EVENT NAME	TYPE	DATES NEXT EDITION	CITY	COUNTRY
European Conference on Precision Agriculture	Conference	19- 22 July 2021	Budapest	Hungary
World Congress of Vine and Wine	Congress	TBD	TBD	TBD
Annual Workshop of EuroGEOSS	Workshop	TBD	Online	Online

EIP-AGRI workshops	Workshops	TBD	Online Belgium /	Online
Inspire Conference	Conference	7-9 September 2021	Dubrovnik	Croatia
International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium	Conference	12-16 July 2021	Online	Online
EU Green Week	Conference / Workshop	June 2021	Online	Online
EARSeL Symposium: EU remote sensing- new solutions	Conference	7-10 June 2021	Warsaw	Poland
EU for Agriculture under pressure workshop	Workshop	TBD	Online	Online
7th International Conference on Geographical Information Systems Theory, Applications and Management - GISTAM 2021	Conference	23-25 April 2021	Online	Online
International Symposium on Environmental Software Systems	Conference	February 2022	TBD	TBD
European Food Forum	Conference	TBD	TBD	TBD
Adaptation Futures	Conference	2022	TBD	TBD
2nd Annual Agritech & Climate Smart Agriculture Conference	Conference	TBD	TBD	TBD

3.6.2 Scientific publications

Reports or outcomes resulting from the project activities will be published in scientific journals related to the project's fields (partners will inform the WP6 leader and Exploitation Manager of the information to be presented publicly to avoid infringement of intellectual property rights).

Partners will ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications published via **gold open access**, whenever available (provided via the publisher when an article is published), and/or **green open access** via an online repository (Open Aire/ Zenodo) to ensure a long-term preservation and availability of the publication.

A VitiGEOSS **Zenodo community will be created** to allocate all VitiGEOSS-related research publications. Publications will be also published in researchers' Research Gate pages (whenever applicable).

An initial list of **open access journals of interest for publishing VitiGEOSS results** has been defined, as follows:

Table 12: List of open access journals

Journal name
Wine & Viticulture Journal - https://winetitles.com.au/wvj/
MPDI Remote Sensing Journal - https://www.mdpi.com/journal/remotesensing
IEEE Advanced Technology for Humanity - https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8977429
International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/international-journal-of-applied-earth-observation-and-geoinformation
Remote Sensing of Environment - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/remote-sensing-of-environment
Agricultural Systems - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/agricultural-systems
Journal of Environmental Management - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-environmental-management
ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/isprs-journal-of-photogrammetry-and-remote-sensing
Computers and Electronics in Agriculture - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/computers-and-electronics-in-agriculture
Journal of Applied Remote Sensing - https://www.spiedigitallibrary.org/journals/journal-of-applied-remote-sensing?SSO=1
Journal of Remote Sensing & GIS https://www.longdom.org/geophysics-remote-sensing.html

3.7 Dissemination to the industry

3.7.1 Participation in industry events

Project partners will also connect with the wine sector in national and international congresses, exhibitions and fairs to disseminate the benefits and potential of VitiGEOSS information services and platform and promote the use of project services and EO within the industry.

A wide range of events are suitable for the exhibition of the VitiGEOSS' results, including the events listed in the following table:

Table 13: Identified events targeting the industry community

EVENT NAME	DATES NEXT EDITION	CITY	COUNTRY
ONEOVITI Symposium	TBD	TBD	TBD
VINITALY	April 2022	Verona	Italy
GIESCO	TBD	TBD	TBS
VINOBLE	May 2022	Jerez de la Frontera	Spain
FENAVIN	May 2022	Ciudad Real	Spain
VINEXPO	June 2021	Paris	France
PROWEIN	March 2022	Dusseldorf	Germany
EXPORIVE	November 2021	Pordenone	Italy
FOOD TECH TRADE	October 2021	Herning	Denmark
ALIMENTARIA	April 2022	Barcelona	Spain

FIMA - International Fair of Agriculture Machinery	February 2022	Zaragoza	Spain
SITEVI	November - December 2021	Montpellier	France
Salon International de l'Agriculture	March 2022	Paris	France
FruitLogistica	February 2022	Berlin	Germany
Events of the INNOVI Cluster	TBD	TBD	TBD
Events of the Technological Platform of wine	TBD	TBD	TBD
Events of the Foundation of Agrofood cooperatives of Catalonia	TBD	TBD	TBD
COPACOGECA events	TBD	TBD	TBD
EuroFruit	September 2021	Lleida	Spain

3.7.2 Technical webinars

The project will organise **three technical webinars addressed to service providers** with the idea of fostering the possibility of exploitation of some particular components of the VitiGEOSS platform within the wine producer community and beyond. The organisation of webinars will be led by BSC, with the support of EUT. Presentations will be delivered by technical project partners.

Some details about the webinars are provided in Table 14. Webinars will be announced through the project communication channels (website and social media), and through the VitiGEOSS mailing list. The sessions will be recorded, and recordings will be uploaded to the project's YouTube channel.

After each webinar, evaluation questionnaires will be distributed among participants to assess the satisfaction and requirements for additional webinar topics of interest.

The webinars will be scheduled after the launch of the VitiGEOSS platform (M12) and on dates that do not coincide with busy periods for partners and relevant users, such as the harvest season, to ensure maximum participation and visibility of VitiGEOSS services.

If deemed necessary, an initial introductory webinar will be scheduled to introduce the project and background information, and to ensure that relevant users and stakeholders understand the project objectives, research and expected outcomes. The introductory webinar can be used to create expectation and encourage the target audiences to attend the next technical webinars.

Details on the general topic of the webinars and tentative dates are listed below, although they can be adjusted according to the evolution of the project advancements:

Table 14: Webinars tentative dates and topics

Topic	Partner	Approximate date
Introductory webinar on VitiGEOSS project and main objectives	EUT, BSC	First trimester 2022
Data analysis in agriculture	EUT	Second trimester of 2022
Probabilistic climate predictions	BSC	First trimester of 2023
Use of satellite data in agriculture	ELEAF	Second trimester of 2023

3.7.3 Local stakeholder sessions

A total of three local stakeholder sessions will be organised by end-users **MBD**, **MTSA** and **SYM** at their premises during the project general assemblies. The organisation of these sessions will be supported by EUT and UNINA.

Sessions will be addressed to **local farmers and rural communities** with the aim to educate on sustainable agricultural practices to improve productivity. These sessions will bring together **professionals from the vineyard sector and the data collection sector** to present them the capabilities and opportunities of the new sensing methods and train them about how to properly apply these technologies in their own fields.

Beyond the outreach purpose of the event, the joint participation of professionals from both disciplines will give them the opportunity to share experiences, aims and requests in order to adapt the offer from providers to the expectations of the vineyard sector practitioners.

Table 15: Preliminary dates of local stakeholder sessions

Stakeholder session	Responsible partner	Approximate timing
1 st GA	MBD (to be confirmed)	M15-16 (November-December 2021)
2 nd GA	MTSA (to be confirmed)	M27-28 (November-December 2022)
3 rd GA	SYM (to be confirmed)	M39-40 (November-December 2023)

3.7.4 Participatory workshops

Two participatory workshops will be delivered during the second half of the project to share lessons learned, present the platform to the wine community and disseminate the main project achievements, with focus on spreading the use of Earth Observation services. The workshop organisation will be led by ELEAF.

Workshops may include seminars and/or training courses on topics relevant to stakeholders to be able to exploit the project platform, such as geo/remote sensing in agriculture (eLEAF), application of remote sensing and EO in viticulture (UNINA) and probabilistic climate forecasts for decision-making (BSC).

The workshops will be organised as side events of renowned fairs or conferences to take advantage of their audiences. They will be addressed to technology developers and commercialisation partners, supported with the presence of relevant stakeholders of the wine and the agriculture sector, as well as EuroGEOSS and Copernicus members, and relevant partners of other related H2020 projects. Collaboration with e-Shape, NextLand, ENVISION, FIRE and other identified projects (see section 3.8.1) will be established to promote participation of the coordinators of these projects in our workshops.

Table 16: Planned workshops

Workshop	Responsible Partners	Approximate timing
Annual Agritech & Climate Smart Agriculture (location TBD)	Lead: ELEAF Contributors: BSC, UNINA (and other partners)	November 2023
FruitLogistica (Berlin, Germany)	Lead: ELEAF Contributors: BSC, UNINA (and other partners)	February 2023

3.8 Dissemination to the society

Participation to events or initiatives for the general public to generate awareness on electric vehicles and batteries:

- **International Wine Days** - Take advantage of the international wine days. Identified list of days of interest for VitiGEOSS project include the International Wine Day (each 25th May), the International Shirah day (each 22nd July), the Global Drink Wine Day (each February 18th).
- **Pint of Science** - <https://pintofscience.com> (*each May*) The Pint of Science festival aims to deliver interesting and relevant talks on the latest science research in an accessible format to the public - mainly across bars, pubs, cafes and other public spaces. We want to provide a platform which allows people to discuss research with the people who carry it out and no prior knowledge of the subject is required.

3.9 Clustering activities and joint dissemination actions

During the VitiGEOSS project execution, project partners will be in contact with the coordinators of other related projects, relevant industry associations and companies, and European institutions related to the project's fields.

Synergies between VitiGEOSS and other groups will be established through attending relevant events or working groups that are organised or attended by the institutions listed in the sections below. Additionally, partners will actively interact with the initiatives promoted by these groups and contribute with content on the project to feed associations' newsletters and publications, when possible.

3.9.1 Sister projects

Connections with other projects, initiatives and knowledge hubs with complementary interests will be sought at national, EU and international level with the aim of enhancing synergies while avoiding duplication of efforts in the dissemination of results.

Partnering with other projects and initiatives will allow to join efforts and also have a stronger voice when communicating with target audiences. Some of the VitiGEOSS sister projects and

initiatives identified to date, related to the agriculture and wine sectors, climate services and/or Earth Observations, are listed in Table 17.

Table 17: VitiGEOSS sister projects

Initiative	Short description	URL
MED-GOLD	Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional Mediterranean grape, olive and durum wheat food systems	https://www.med-gold.eu/
VISCA	Climate services and Decision Support System that integrate climate, agricultural models and farmers' management specifications to adapt to climate change	https://www.visca.eu/
MEDCLIV	Experimenting with participatory approaches to design and share co-constructed adaptation (and to some extent mitigation) pathways for the vine and wine value chain in Mediterranean territories	https://medcliv.ibe.cnr.it/
AgROBOfood	New European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) to stimulate the implementation of high robotic technologies and Artificial Intelligence in the agri-food industry.	https://agrobofood.eu
IoECrops	The IoECrops project improves the productivity, efficiency and resilience of large-scale crop production by supporting agricultural management through the use of technologies based on the Internet of Things (IoT).	https://eurecat.org/en/portfolio-items/ioe-crops/
E-Shape	e-shape is one of the nine EU-funded Environmental Observations projects that contribute to upscale Europe's Environmental Observations capacities.	https://e-shape.eu
NextGEOSS	NextGEOSS is a centralised European Earth observation data hub and platform. The concept revolves around providing the data and ICT resources needed, together with cloud services, seamlessly connected to provide an integrated ecosystem to support the	https://nextgeoss.eu/

	deployment of Earth observation-based applications and services.	
Climate-Smart Agriculture Booster	The Climate-smart Agriculture Booster or CSA Booster is Europe's leading innovation hub, community and collaboration platform pioneering the transition to climate-smart agriculture across Europe, and around the world.	http://csabooster.climate-kic.org
ENVISION	Monitoring of environmental practices for sustainable agriculture supported by earth observation	https://envision-h2020.eu
NextLand	Next Generation land management services for agriculture and forestry	https://ec-nextland.eu
FIRE	An industry-led forum for innovation and research in EU earth observation	
SAFERS	Structured approaches for forest fire emergencies in resilient societies	https://safers-project.eu
SUSTUNTECH	Sustainable tuna fisheries through advanced earth observation technologies	https://www.sustuntech.eu
Coppereplace	Development and validation of a series of integrated, innovative, and viable solutions to reduce the use of copper and its environmental impact in vineyards.	http://coppereplace.com
Innoseta Network	Innovative self-sustainable Thematic Network on Spraying Equipment, Training and Advising to contribute in closing the gap between the available novel high-end crop protection solutions with the everyday European agricultural practices.	http://www.innoseta.eu/aim/

Specifically, VitiGEOSS will interact with EuroGEOSS by joining two actions groups (climate and agriculture), as well as with NextGEOSS by contributing to their data catalogue. The VitiGEOSS project will also actively participate in e-Shape project workshops and related activities.

Up to M7 the project was presented at the e-shape project General Assembly celebrated in an online format between 19th - 21st October 2020.

The collaboration with other projects and initiatives will allow to identify aspects from VitiGEOSS beyond the final project products that may be of interest to other communities. In this sense, the main lessons learned in the project for the climate services and the Earth Observation communities will be summarized in D6.7 and shared with these communities.

3.9.2 EU initiatives and key platforms

Cooperation and synergies will be established with relevant initiatives and platforms, some of which are listed below:

- **International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV)** - <https://www.oiv.int/en> - The OIV is an intergovernmental organisation of a scientific and technical nature of recognised competence for its work concerning vines, wine, wine-based beverages, table grapes, raisins and other vine-based products.
- **EU Green Deal** - https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en - The European Green Deal is the latest European plan for responding to climate change challenges by seeking carbon neutrality, and improving the well-being of people by protecting our natural habitat, among other goals.
- **COPA-COGECA** - <https://copa-cogeca.eu> - Copa (the Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations) represents over 22 million European farmers and their family members in a combined effort with its members to promote the best interests of the agricultural sector among the EU institutions and other relevant stakeholders. Cogeca (the General Confederation of Agricultural Cooperatives) represents the general and specific interests of European agri-food, forestry, and fishery cooperatives among EU institutions and other socio-economic organisations contributing to European decision making.
- **Comité Européen des entreprises vins** - www.ceev.eu - CEEV is the representative professional body of the EU industry and trade in wine gathering 23 national associations and more than 7.000 companies, mainly SMEs, producing and selling the large majority of EU quality wines, with and without geographical indications.
- **EuroGEO** - EuroGEO is Europe's part of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO), a worldwide network working to build a Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS). EuroGEO enables Europe to position itself as a global force in Earth observation thanks to the vast knowledge gained through running the Copernicus programme and others.
- **The European Technology Platform "Food for Life"** - The Food for Life Technological Platform is the promotion of the transmission of research, scientific and technological advances through public-private collaboration of the main agri-food sector agents in relation to R&D+I and the detection of new demands in the field of Society Challenges, ensuring the competitiveness and growth of the Spanish agri-food sector.

4. Activities calendar

ACTIVITIES	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
	Mar-21	Apr-21	May-21	Jun-21	Jul-21	Aug-21	Sep-21	Oct-21	Nov-21	Dec-21	Jan-22	Feb-22
D6.9 Communication and Dissemination Plan	X											
D6.3 Initial summary report on user engagement activities						X						
Short video interviews						X	X	X	X	X	X	X
1 st Press release				X								
Local stakeholder session 1 (Italy)									X	X		
D6.10 Communication and dissemination plan - Final report												X
Technical webinar 1: Introductory webinar on VitiGEOSS project and main objectives											X	X
	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30
	Mar-22	Apr-22	May-22	Jun-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	Sep-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Jan-23	Feb-23
Promotional materials update (infosheet, trifold, general presentation)		X										
Poster production		X										

2nd press release: release intelligent services		X										
Technical webinar 2: Data analysis in agriculture	X	X	X									
Poster translation into pilot sites languages			X									
Demo video production	X	X	X	X	X							
D6.6 Demo Video						X						
Local stakeholder session (Spain)									X	X		
D6.2 Middle Summary report of user engagement activities									X			
Technical webinar 3: Probabilistic Climate Predictions											X	X
3 rd press release: Start of services validation in pilot sites												X
Participatory workshop at FruitLogistica												X
	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42
	Mar-23	Apr-23	May-23	Jun-23	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24	Feb-24
Technical webinar 4: Use of satellite data in agriculture	X	X										
Promotional materials update (infosheet, trifold, general presentation)		X								X		
Production of infosheets on information services (update by M40)		X	X							X	X	X
D6.7 Lessons learned in VITIGEOSS for Climate Services and Earth Observations Communities						X						
D6.12 Summary report						X						

on dissemination and communication activities and materials (1st version)													
2 nd demo video production							X	X	X				
Local stakeholder session (Portugal)									X	X			
Participatory workshop 2: Agritech & Climate Smart Agriculture									X				
D6.11 Demo video second version										X			
Final video										X	X	X	
4 th press release: platform release										X			
5 th press release: final project results													X
D6.4 Summary report on dissemination and communication activities and materials													X
D6.5 Final summary report on user engagement activities													X
D6.8 Executive Summary													X

